

1 **USING DIRECTED ACYCLIC GRAPHS TO ASSESS COLLIDER AND CONFOUNDING BIAS**
2 **IN REVIEWS OF OBSERVATIONAL STUDIES: AN ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE USING THE**
3 **IMPACT OF RESIDENTIAL EXPOSURE TO ANIMAL FEEDING OPERATIONS ON HUMAN**
4 **HEALTH**

5

6 **ABSTRACT**

7 **Background**

8 Bias assessment in systematic reviews of observational studies commonly includes
9 consideration about whether key confounders were controlled but rarely evaluates whether
10 control strategies may have introduced bias through control of colliders or mediators. In primary
11 observational research, directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) are used to explicitly represent
12 hypothesized causal structures, identify variables required to block non-causal (biasing)
13 pathways, and distinguish confounders from variables that should not be controlled for. How
14 DAG-based reasoning can be systematically incorporated into bias assessment during evidence
15 synthesis remains insufficiently explored.

16 **Objective**

17 The primary objective of this study was to demonstrate how an existing, population-level DAG
18 can be used as a reference framework to assess potential confounding and control-related bias
19 in a systematic review of observational studies. The secondary objective was to evaluate
20 whether primary studies reported a rationale for covariate selection.

21 **Methods**

22 We examined a subset of observational studies identified through a living systematic review
23 assessing community health effects associated with residential proximity to animal feeding
24 operations (AFOs). Studies were eligible if they sought to estimate a causal effect. For studies
25 examining lower respiratory outcomes, covariates reported by study authors were mapped onto
26 nodes in a previously published population-level DAG. The DAG was then used to assess
27 whether reported control strategies were theoretically sufficient to block non-causal pathways
28 and whether control for colliders or other inappropriate variables may have occurred. We also
29 reviewed each study for explicit justification of covariate selection.

30 **Results**

31 Among 36 studies identified in the parent review, 17 reported incident outcomes and met the
32 inclusion criteria. None of the included studies reported using a DAG or an explicit causal

33 framework to guide covariate selection. Eight studies examined lower respiratory outcomes and
34 could be evaluated using the reference DAG. In six of these studies, control for at least one
35 variable identified as a collider in the reference DAG opened a non-causal pathway between
36 exposure and outcome. In the remaining two studies, it was unclear whether potential
37 confounding pathways, particularly those related to socioeconomic factors, were addressed
38 through study design or population characteristics, precluding firm conclusions.

39 **Conclusions**

40 This study illustrates how DAG-based reasoning, using a pre-existing population-level causal
41 diagram, can complement conventional risk-of-bias approaches in systematic reviews by
42 making assumptions about confounding and inappropriate control explicit. Incorporating DAGs
43 into evidence synthesis may improve transparency in bias assessment and support more
44 interpretable causal reasoning in reviews of observational studies.

45 **Keywords:** Directed Acyclic Graphs, agriculture, Causal Effect, Confounding, Observational
46 Studies

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74 **INTRODUCTION**

75 Observational studies encompass a wide range of designs and purposes, including descriptive,
76 surveillance, hypothesis-generating and hypothesis-testing research. In many applied fields,
77 however, observational data are also commonly used to address questions that are causal in
78 nature, particularly when randomized controlled trials are infeasible, unethical, or impractical. In
79 such settings, researchers often seek to estimate the effect of an exposure on a health outcome
80 using observational designs, even if this causal objective is not always made explicit (Hernán,
81 2018).

82 When observational studies are interpreted as providing evidence about causal effects, the
83 distinction between causation and confounding becomes critical. Without explicit articulation of
84 the assumed causal structure underlying an exposure–outcome relationship, conventional
85 multivariable adjustment strategies may inadvertently introduce bias through incomplete control
86 of confounding or through inappropriate control for variables such as mediators or colliders. This
87 challenge has been widely documented across applied epidemiologic research, where
88 traditional definitions of confounding and automated variable selection procedures can leave
89 investigators vulnerable to controlling the wrong types of variables (Correia et al., 2025; Parra et
90 al., 2021). As a result, formal causal reasoning frameworks have been increasingly emphasized
91 as a means to improve transparency and validity in observational causal inference (Churilov et
92 al., 2025; Gail et al., 2019). Directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) are one such framework. In primary
93 observational research, DAGs are increasingly used to make explicit the hypothesized causal
94 structure linking an exposure and an outcome, thereby supporting the identification of variables
95 that may require control to estimate a causal effect, as well as variables that should not be
96 controlled because doing so could introduce bias (Tennant et al., 2021; Digitale et al., 2023).
97 Importantly, the utility of a DAG is contingent on some assumptions. First, the specified graph
98 must reasonably reflect the underlying data-generating mechanisms operating in the target
99 population—that is, the real causal processes that produce the observed patterns of exposure,
100 covariates, and outcomes in the population, which the DAG is intended to approximate. Second,
101 conditioning on variables must occur only through explicit analytical decisions such as statistical
102 adjustment rather than implicitly through sample selection, restriction, or stratification. These
103 assumptions represent necessary preconditions for using DAGs to reason about confounding
104 and other sources of bias (Digitale et al., 2022; Hernán and Robins, 2020; Sauer and
105 VanderWeele, 2013).

106 Our motivation for exploring how DAGs could help reviewers conduct a comprehensive bias
107 assessment stem from our experience with two previous systematic reviews on this topic, where
108 evaluating bias, particularly in relation to confounding, has been a central and especially
109 challenging aspect of the analysis. Usually confounding bias assessment is limited to “Did the
110 authors include the main confounders?”, an approach reflected in several risk-of-bias
111 frameworks, including ROBINS-E (Higgins et al. 2024). However, such an approach does not
112 account for the complex pathways that might exist in causal questions, and therefore we were
113 interested in different assessment methods or tools. The challenge lies, however, not only in
114 identifying and controlling for true confounders, but also in avoiding the erroneous control for
115 other types of variables, such as colliders and mediators, which can introduce bias rather than
116 reduce it (Digitale et al., 2023; Tennant et al., 2021). An additional motivation for incorporating
117 DAG-based reasoning into evidence synthesis is the central role of systematic reviews in causal
118 assessment. Causal inference in observational research should not rely on single studies in
119 isolation, even when those studies employ rigorous analytical methods. Rather, causal
120 interpretation emerges through the synthesis of evidence across multiple studies, making
121 transparent evaluation of assumptions, sources of bias, and analytic choices essential at the
122 review level.

123 Within evidence synthesis, DAGs can be used in conceptually distinct ways. Reviewers may (i)
124 construct a synthesized DAG de novo using background knowledge and evidence across
125 studies; (ii) rely on study-specific DAGs reported by primary investigators to assess control
126 decisions within each study’s stated causal framework; or (iii) adopt an existing, published
127 population-level DAG as a reference causal model and evaluate whether the control strategies
128 used in included studies are compatible with that model. Each approach has different
129 methodological implications and resource requirements; thus, the choice among these
130 approaches depends on the review question, the availability of existing causal models, and the
131 level at which causal assumptions are to be evaluated. By ‘level,’ we refer to whether causal
132 assumptions are examined at the level of individual primary studies, or at a broader population
133 level using a shared causal framework against which multiple studies are evaluated.

134 When used at the target population level, DAGs encode assumptions about how exposures,
135 outcomes, confounders, mediators, colliders, and other variables are causally related in the real
136 world, independent of any specific study design or measurement process (Williams et al., 2018;
137 Bours, 2021). By explicitly representing hypothesized causal and non-causal pathways, DAGs
138 allow investigators and reviewers to reason systematically about which variables should be

139 controlled to block biasing (backdoor) paths while preserving causal pathways of interest
140 (Bours, 2021; Williams et al., 2018).

141 A key concept underlying the use of DAGs is d-separation, which provides a formal criterion for
142 determining whether a set of variables blocks all non-causal pathways between an exposure
143 and an outcome (Pearl, 2009; Textor et al., 2016). Two variables are considered d-separated if
144 all paths connecting them are blocked through conditioning on an appropriate set of variables,
145 such that any remaining association can be interpreted as causal under the assumed DAG. In
146 applied epidemiologic research, d-separation allows investigators and reviewers to evaluate
147 whether a reported set of control variables are theoretically sufficient to control confounding
148 while avoiding inappropriate control for mediators or colliders that could induce bias (Cole et al.,
149 2010; Hernán & Robins, 2020). Variables that influence both the exposure and the outcome
150 function as confounders and require control to prevent spurious associations. By contrast,
151 mediators are intermediate variables through which the exposure exerts its effect on the
152 outcome and should not be controlled for when the goal is to estimate the total effect.
153 Colliders—variables that arise as a consequence of two or more preceding causes—should also
154 typically not be conditioned on, because doing so can induce associations along paths that
155 would otherwise remain closed (Cole et al., 2010; Hernán & Robins, 2020).

156 In the context of evidence synthesis, assessing if a study has controlled for confounding using
157 DAGs and the concept of d-separation could provide a principled way to assess whether study-
158 specific control strategies are capable, *in theory*, of closing biasing pathways, independent of
159 statistical significance or effect magnitude. This perspective is particularly relevant for reviews of
160 observational studies, where determining whether confounding has been adequately addressed
161 requires explicit consideration of causal assumptions rather than reliance on variable lists or
162 model-building heuristics alone.

163 In this manuscript, we focus on the use of an existing, externally developed conceptual DAG,
164 originally proposed to represent the population-level causal structure linking AFO-related
165 exposures to respiratory health outcomes, as a methodological tool for bias assessment in a
166 systematic review context. We did not modify the DAG or construct a synthesis or study-specific
167 DAG. Instead, we used the published DAG as a reference model to illustrate how different control
168 choices reported in primary studies may open or close biasing paths under the assumed causal
169 structure. By doing so, we aim to demonstrate how DAG-based reasoning can complement

170 existing risk-of-bias approaches and provide greater conceptual transparency when interpreting
171 observational evidence on AFO exposures and community health.

172 173 **OBJECTIVES**

174 The objective of this study was to demonstrate how an existing, unmodified, population-level
175 directed acyclic graph (DAG) can be used as a reference framework for assessing potential
176 confounding and adjustment-related bias in evidence synthesis of observational studies that are
177 intended for, or commonly interpreted as, causal inference. Using published studies examining
178 associations between exposure to animal feeding operations (AFOs) and community respiratory
179 health as an illustrative example, we evaluate whether control strategies reported in primary
180 studies are compatible with the assumed population-level causal structure represented by the
181 DAG. The secondary objective was to evaluate whether primary studies reported a rationale for
182 covariate selection.

183 This work does not aim to derive a new causal model, construct a synthesis- or study-specific
184 DAG, or estimate causal effects. Rather, its purpose is methodological: to illustrate how DAG-
185 based reasoning may complement conventional risk-of-bias assessment in evidence synthesis
186 by improving transparency in the evaluation of confounding and inappropriate control.

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188 **METHODS**

189 **Source of studies and sampling strategy**

190 The studies included in this analysis represent a subset of those identified in a living systematic
191 review (LSR) assessing the health effects of Animal Feeding Operations (AFOs) on nearby
192 communities. The methods for the LSR, including search strategies, screening procedures, and
193 eligibility criteria, are described in a publicly available protocol ([https://syreaf.org/wp-
194 content/uploads/2022/05/Draft_Protocol_CAFO-3.pdf](https://syreaf.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Draft_Protocol_CAFO-3.pdf)).

195 From the pool of studies identified through abstract and full-text screening, we selected
196 observational studies that evaluated associations between residential exposure to AFOs and
197 incident health outcomes, including outcomes affecting the lower respiratory tract, upper
198 respiratory tract, antibiotic resistance, gastrointestinal disease, and infectious diseases. Studies
199 were included if, based on the reported analytic approach, the review team judged that the
200 effect estimates were intended to reflect the occurrence of new health events following
201 exposure. **For the purposes of this demonstration, an incident outcome was defined as the first
202 occurrence of a lower respiratory disease event during follow-up among individuals initially free**

203 of the outcome. Restricting inclusion to studies assessing incident outcomes ensured
204 appropriate temporality between exposure and outcome, a prerequisite for causal interpretation
205 and for constructing DAGs that reflect hypothesized causal ordering.

206 **Adoption of a population-level DAG for the review**

207 For the purposes of this review, we adopted a single, population-level DAG to represent the
208 assumed causal structure linking residential exposure to AFOs and respiratory health outcomes
209 in nearby communities. Specifically, we adopted the DAG developed by Brewer et al. (2017) as
210 the synthesized causal model for the review. Throughout this review, 'residential exposure to
211 AFOs' is treated as the underlying exposure construct; study-specific measures such as self-
212 reported odor or modeled emissions are considered proxy operationalizations of this construct,
213 consistent with the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG. The Brewer et al. DAG was selected for three
214 reasons (Figure 1). First, it is, to our knowledge, the only published DAG explicitly developed for
215 the AFO community respiratory health context. Second, it was constructed using domain
216 expertise and background knowledge relevant to environmental exposures and respiratory
217 outcomes at the population level, rather than being tied to a specific study design. Third, the
218 DAG was developed independently of the present review, reducing the risk that it reflects post-
219 hoc adaptation to the included studies. The reference DAG was used without structural
220 modification. For clarity of presentation, its nodes were visually reorganized to emphasize a
221 temporal ordering. This visual reorganization was intended to aid interpretation and did not alter
222 the causal assumptions encoded in the DAG or introduce additional analytic steps.

223 By adopting this DAG, we make explicit the causal assumptions under which control strategies
224 in the included studies were evaluated. The DAG represents population-level causal
225 relationships and does not incorporate study-specific features such as selection mechanisms or
226 measurement error. This DAG represents causal constructs rather than study-specific
227 measured variables. Accordingly, variables reported in each primary study (e.g., odor reports,
228 distance to facilities, education) were evaluated as imperfect proxies for these constructs and
229 mapped to existing DAG nodes, rather than introduced as separate measured nodes.

230 **Approach to the analysis of the primary objective**

231 For each included study, we assessed whether the variables reported as controlled would,
232 under the Brewer et al. DAG, block all non-causal (biasing) pathways between exposure and
233 outcome without introducing bias through inappropriate conditioning.

234 This assessment was based on principles of graphical causal analysis, using d-separation as
235 the criterion for determining whether sets of control variables were theoretically sufficient to
236 close backdoor paths while leaving causal pathways unblocked. Importantly, this evaluation is
237 independent of statistical significance, effect magnitude, or automated variable-selection
238 procedures. Instead, it relies on the theoretical compatibility between reported analytical
239 decisions and the assumed causal structure.

240 **Implementation of the DAG-based bias assessment**

241 For each included study, information was extracted from the Methods and Statistical Analysis
242 sections to identify the exposure variable(s), outcome variable(s), and all variables reported as
243 controlled. Study-specific exposure measures (e.g., self-reported odor, distance to the nearest
244 AFO, or density of AFOs) were treated as proxies for the exposure construct represented in the
245 adopted DAG. Similarly, respiratory outcomes reported in individual studies were mapped to the
246 outcome node in the DAG based on conceptual equivalence.

247 Variables controlled for in each study were mapped to corresponding nodes in the DAG based
248 on conceptual meaning rather than exact terminology. When different labels were used across
249 studies (e.g., “household income,” “economic status,” or “poverty-to-income ratio”), these were
250 mapped to the appropriate socioeconomic construct represented in the DAG. When a reported
251 control variable could not be plausibly mapped to an existing node in the adopted DAG, it was
252 not incorporated into the DAG-based bias assessment. Such variables were instead
253 documented in the Results.

254 Although the conceptual assessment of bias relied on graphical causal reasoning and the rules
255 of d-separation, the practical implementation of this assessment was supported using DAGitty
256 software (Textor et al., 2016). DAGitty was used to encode the adopted DAG, indicate
257 conditioned variables for each study, and systematically identify open backdoor paths. The use
258 of DAGitty served as an analytical aid rather than a requirement of the method; the underlying
259 logic of the assessment is independent of any specific software tool.

260 **Evaluation of confounding and inappropriate control**

261 Using the mapped DAG for each study, we evaluated whether the reported control strategy was
262 theoretically sufficient to block all non-causal (biasing) pathways between exposure and
263 outcome. This evaluation focused on identifying:

- 264 • potential uncontrolled confounding, indicated by open backdoor paths remaining after
265 control; and
- 266 • potential inappropriate control, such as conditioning on variables that act as mediators or
267 colliders within the assumed causal structure.

268 The assessment was structural and theoretical, relying solely on the causal assumptions
269 encoded in the adopted DAG and the variables reported as controlled in each study. No re-
270 estimation of effect sizes was performed, and no modifications were made to the adopted DAG.

271 **Analytical assumptions**

272 The approach illustrated in this study rests on several analytical assumptions that warrant
273 explicit acknowledgement. First, it assumes the availability of a DAG that plausibly represents
274 the relevant population-level causal structure linking exposure and outcome. Second, it
275 assumes that at least some of the variables depicted in the DAG are observable and reported
276 with sufficient clarity in primary studies to permit a meaningful assessment of whether the set of
277 variables controlled for in each study satisfies the d-separation criterion implied by the Brewer et
278 al. DAG. Third, it assumes methodological comparability across studies, particularly with respect
279 to outcome definition, exposure operationalization, and analytical conditioning decisions, such
280 that potential sources of confounding or collider bias can be evaluated in a consistent manner.
281 These assumptions are treated as analytical priors for the illustrative review presented here.

282 **Assessment of reporting rationale for covariate selection (secondary objective)**

283 To address the secondary objective, we reviewed the Methods and Statistical Analysis sections
284 of each included study to determine whether authors reported an explicit rationale for covariate
285 identification, selection, or retention. A rationale was considered present if authors described a
286 *priori* criteria, model-building strategies, or decision rules guiding covariate inclusion. Studies
287 were classified according to whether such a rationale was reported. This assessment evaluated
288 reporting practices only and did not judge the appropriateness of selected covariates.

289 **RESULTS**

291 **Study Identification and Inclusion**

292 The flow chart for the original systematic review is provided in the supplementary materials. The
293 original review found 36 studies that reported prevalent or incident outcomes. Of those 36
294 observational studies, 17 studies met the eligibility criteria for this methodological assessment,
295 namely the evaluation of incident health outcomes. None of the 17 included studies reported an

296 explicit causal diagram or articulated a causal model underlying their analytic approach. Key
297 characteristics of the included studies are summarized in Table 1.

298 **Results of Primary Objective**

299 Of the 17 studies, 10 examined lower respiratory tract outcomes (Radon et al. 2005; Mirabelli et
300 al. 2006; Hoopmann et al. 2006; Radon et al. 2007; Smit et al. 2012; Hooiveld et al. 2016; Freidl
301 et al. 2017; Rasmussen et al. 2017; Schultz et al. 2019; van Kersen et al. 2020). For these
302 outcomes, the population-level DAG published by Brewer et al. (2017) served as the reference
303 causal structure for the primary analysis. One study focused on Q-fever–associated pneumonia
304 (Smit et al., 2012) and was excluded from DAG-based assessment because the causal pathway
305 for this outcome involves a distinct infectious mechanism not represented in the Brewer DAG.
306 One Dutch cohort study employed a self-controlled design in which each participant served as
307 their own control (van Kersen et al., 2020). This design estimates a within-person causal effect
308 by leveraging temporal variation in exposure and implicitly controls for all time-invariant
309 confounders by design. As such, the causal estimand targeted by this study differs
310 fundamentally from the between-person estimands addressed by the other included
311 observational studies. Because the adopted population-level DAG represents hypothesized
312 between-person causal relationships and confounding structures, it is not appropriate for
313 evaluating studies targeting within-person estimands. For this reason, the van Kersen et al.
314 (2020) study was not evaluated using the DAG-based framework applied to the remaining eight
315 studies.

316 **Compatibility of Control Strategies with the Reference DAG**

317 Table 2 summarizes the variables controlled for in each of the eight studies evaluated against
318 the reference DAG. Across studies, authors controlled for a wide range of demographic,
319 environmental, and socioeconomic variables. Many of these variables were not represented in
320 the Brewer et al. DAG.

321 When mapped descriptively to the reference DAG, none of the eight studies controlled for a
322 complete set of variables that would specifically create d-separation conditions (Figure 2-9). In
323 several studies, the set of control variables omitted variables represented as common causes in
324 the reference DAG (e.g., socioeconomic factors), while simultaneously including variables that
325 occupy non-confounding positions within that structure. In six of the eight studies, smoking-
326 related variables were included in the set of control variables (Radon et al. 2005; Mirabelli et al.
327 2006; Hoopmann et al. 2006; Radon et al. 2007; Rasmussen et al. 2017; Schultz et al. 2019). In

328 the reference DAG, smoking is positioned as a collider on at least one pathway linking
329 socioeconomic factors to respiratory outcomes. Conditioning on such a variable is therefore
330 theoretically incompatible with the causal structure assumed in the reference DAG and opens
331 biasing pathways under that model.

332 In the remaining two studies, neither smoking nor key socioeconomic variables were included in
333 the set of control variables (Freidl et al. 2017, Hooiveld et al 2016). Given that the reference
334 DAG represents a population-level structure and does not encode country-specific design
335 features or restrictions, it was not possible to determine whether these variables were implicitly
336 controlled through study design or population homogeneity. As a result, no definitive conclusion
337 could be drawn regarding compatibility with the reference DAG in these cases. Overall, none of
338 the evaluated studies reported control strategies that were fully compatible with the population-
339 level causal structure represented by the Brewer et al. DAG.

340

341

342 **Results of Secondary Objective**

343 In all the 17 studies, researchers employed multivariable models and adjusted for potential
344 confounding variables. Of the 17 studies, only three provided a rationale for selecting and
345 retaining potential confounding variables. Schultz et al. (2019), Freidl et al. (2017), and Simões
346 et al. (2022) specified criteria for retaining covariates in the multivariable model, primarily based
347 on a change in the main effect estimate exceeding 10%. Of these, Schultz et al. (2019) and
348 Freidl et al. (2017) were among the eight studies evaluated in relation to the Brewer et al. DAG.
349 Freidl et al. (2017) reported that covariates with a p-value less than 0.15 were included in the
350 multivariable analyses. Freidl et al. (2017) and Simões et al. (2022) specified that three
351 multivariable models were developed with different covariates. Upon evaluation, they observed
352 minimal disparity in the magnitude of effect among the three controlled models. Consequently,
353 they selected the model with the least number of confounding variables (age and gender) for
354 reporting purposes. The remaining references included potential confounding variables in their
355 statistical model without specifying their identification process or utilizing model-building
356 strategies. In studies examining diseases affecting various body systems (e.g., digestive and
357 respiratory), no evidence was found indicating different causal pathways or hypotheses.

358 **DISCUSSION**

359

360 In this study, we illustrated how an existing, population-level DAG can be used as a reference
361 framework to evaluate control strategies reported in observational studies included in a systematic
362 review. Applying the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG to studies examining associations between
363 exposure to animal feeding operations (AFOs) and lower respiratory outcomes, we found that
364 none of the evaluated studies reported sets of control variables that were fully compatible with
365 the causal structure assumed in the reference DAG. This observation held, despite the
366 widespread use of multivariable adjustment and despite authors' apparent intent to control for
367 confounding. **The visual reorganization of the reference DAG to highlight temporality was intended
368 to improve interpretability rather than to redefine confounder status, and all assessments remain
369 conditional on the original causal structure proposed by Brewer et al.**

370 Specifically, when the modified Brewer et al. (2017) DAG is taken as a reasonable
371 representation of the hypothesized causal relationships linking aerosol emissions from AFOs to
372 lower respiratory outcomes, all evaluated studies exhibited at least one remaining open pathway
373 or controlled for variables whose role in the causal structure is ambiguous. Importantly, this
374 does not imply that the reported estimates are necessarily biased in truth; rather, it indicates
375 that, under the assumptions encoded in the reference DAG, the control strategies used do not
376 clearly correspond to a minimum sufficient set of control variables.

377 A recurrent illustration of this issue involves smoking, which was frequently included as a
378 covariate based on its well-established association with respiratory disease. Under the assumed
379 causal structure encoded in the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, however, conditioning on smoking
380 opens a non-causal pathway between exposure and outcome. This example illustrates how
381 control decisions that are epidemiologically intuitive can, under certain causal assumptions,
382 complicate causal interpretation. Importantly, our objective was not to determine whether
383 smoking truly functions as a collider in this setting, but to demonstrate how DAG-based
384 reasoning allows reviewers to make the implications of such control choices explicit when
385 evaluating potential sources of bias.

386 **Outcome-Specific Causal Structures and Control Practices**

387 Many studies covered a broad spectrum of health outcomes, encompassing respiratory,
388 gastrointestinal, and infectious conditions in a single study. Control in these studies was
389 performed using the same of control variables. However, it remains unclear how those identical
390 covariates could be considered confounding factors in the associations between residing near

391 an AFO and outcome categories beyond lower respiratory tract disease (Martinez 2023). For
392 instance, Hooiveld et al. (2016) studied gastroenteritis-presumed infection, asthma, and chronic
393 enteritis, adjusting for the same set of confounders (“age,” “gender,” “duration of registration,”
394 “number of inhabitants in the zip code area,” and “total surface area”) across all outcomes. It
395 remains uncertain whether the causal pathways for these outcomes were replicated using
396 DAGs, although such a modeling approach would seem reasonable. This observation does not
397 imply that such analyses are invalid, but rather that their interpretation would benefit from
398 clearer articulation of the causal assumptions underpinning each exposure–outcome
399 relationship. DAGs provide one mechanism for making those assumptions explicit and for
400 distinguishing between confounders, mediators, colliders, and proxies across different
401 outcomes.

402 The application of a population-level DAG highlights the importance of context when interpreting
403 confounding. The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG was developed to represent hypothesized causal
404 relationships in a U.S. setting and may not fully capture causal structures operating in other
405 countries. For example, a study conducted in the Netherlands did not identify socioeconomic
406 status, assessed as standardized household income, as a confounder of the association
407 between residential proximity to AFOs and respiratory outcomes. From a DAG-based
408 perspective, this discrepancy does not imply that SES is or is not a confounder in any absolute
409 sense, but rather that its role depends on how socioeconomic factors are assumed to influence
410 both exposure and outcome within a given context. Importantly, whether a variable functions as
411 a confounder is determined by the assumed causal structure, specifically whether it is a
412 common cause of exposure and outcome, rather than by empirical criteria such as changes in
413 effect estimates after statistical adjustment. This underscores that DAG-based bias assessment
414 evaluates compatibility with an assumed causal structure, not empirical confirmation of that
415 structure.

416 **Precedent for the approach**

417 This study builds on prior work demonstrating the use of DAGs in evidence synthesis and bias
418 assessment. In 2012, Polzer et al. created their own DAGs to investigate the link between tooth
419 loss and mortality in humans, for which they derived minimum sufficient sets of confounding
420 variables. They then performed a systematic review of the literature and assessed the included
421 studies based on whether they controlled for the appropriate variables. This approach required
422 mapping the variables controlled for in the studies to the variables identified in the minimum
423 sufficient sets by Polzer et al. 2012. In 2025, Tiwari et al. created and published their own DAG

424 to estimate the effect of being small-for-gestational-age on malnutrition in children under five
425 years of age. The key difference between the Polzer et al. (2012) and Tiwari et al. (2025)
426 studies and the current study is that the DAG we used was based on a previously published
427 DAG, rather than one we constructed ourselves. Others have suggested a formal approach to
428 creating DAGs using evidence synthesis methods (Ferguson et al. 2020).
429 Although these methods share the goal of using DAGs to inform bias assessment, they differ in
430 implementation. In this study, we adopted a previously published, population-level DAG rather
431 than constructing a new DAG *de novo*. We identified the DAG developed by Brewer et al.
432 (2017), produced by researchers at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, which explicitly
433 hypothesizes the causal structure linking residence near animal feeding operations and chronic
434 bronchitis. The availability of this independently developed DAG enabled us to evaluate study-
435 specific control strategies against an explicit, externally specified causal framework. This
436 approach illustrates how reviewers may either adopt an existing public DAG or, where none is
437 available, develop one prospectively as part of the review protocol to support transparent bias
438 assessment.

439 **Limitations of using DAGs for bias assessment**

440 Our study has some limitations, with the most significant being the utilization of DAGs for a
441 “treatment” (living near an AFO) that is not mutable. In reality, living near an AFO is not an
442 observable exposure, according to the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, while Odor was an observable
443 variable (Brewer et al. 2017). Technically, DAGs need variables that are both well-defined and
444 amenable to intervention(s) (Tennant et al. 2021). In observational studies of environmental
445 health, defining exposures can pose challenges. We have presumed that all exposure metrics
446 utilized, such as NH₃ or ammonia, pounds of hogs within 3 miles, etc., could potentially be
447 modifiable and clearly defined interventions. However, one may consider that the Brewer et al.
448 (2017) DAG is not a causal diagram under the current state of knowledge given the
449 inconsistency in exposure metrics across this body of work. This inconsistency raises concerns,
450 as ill-defined exposures may yield causal pathways without clear causal interpretations.

451 Second, in the absence of study-specific causal frameworks, we assumed a shared causal
452 structure for lower respiratory outcomes, including chronic bronchitis. This assumption is
453 necessarily provisional and may not hold across populations or disease subtypes. Our findings
454 therefore apply specifically to lower respiratory outcomes evaluated under the reference DAG
455 and should not be generalized to other health domains without additional causal modeling
456 (Martinez 2023). Our assessment evaluated compatibility with an assumed causal structure

457 rather than establishing the presence or absence of bias in a definitive sense. The identification
458 of open pathways or ambiguous adjustments reflects uncertainty about causal interpretation, not
459 proof that reported estimates are incorrect.

460 Although not the primary objective of this paper, our findings highlight the need to improve
461 reporting of justifications for choosing covariates to control in multivariable models, as
462 demonstrated by the results of the secondary objective. DAGs are an increasingly standard
463 method for representing the hypothesized causal relationships among the variables and
464 identifying the minimum sufficient set (Brewer et al. (2017); Tennant et al. 2021). For older
465 studies it might not be reasonable to expect a DAG to be used, as their use has only become
466 more common in the past decade. Further, scrutiny of reporting of variables controlled for in
467 multivariable regression analysis is fairly new. The Strengthening the Reporting of
468 Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE) guidelines (Noah 2008; von Elm et al. 2008)
469 recommend in Item 7 that authors should "Clearly define all outcomes, exposures, predictors,
470 potential confounders, and effect modifiers. Give diagnostic criteria, if applicable." Item 16
471 indicates that authors should "Give unadjusted estimates and, if applicable, confounder-
472 adjusted estimates and their precision (e.g., 95% confidence interval). Make clear which
473 confounders were adjusted for and why they were included." However, the guidance does not
474 include information about DAGs. While none of the authors of the included studies proposed
475 their own DAG, the incorporation and documentation of DAGs or a hypothesized causal
476 pathway guiding the selection of the set of control variables would have enhanced our
477 understanding of the causal relationships hypothesized by the authors.

478 Beyond the conceptual and reporting challenges discussed above, several residual sources of
479 bias remain even when a temporality-informed DAG is used to appraise covariate adjustment
480 strategies. First, residual confounding is likely due to unmeasured or poorly measured variables,
481 particularly when primary studies provide limited justification for covariate selection or lack
482 information on causal ordering. Second, selection bias may arise from study participation,
483 healthcare access, or analytic restrictions, including forms of endogenous selection that can
484 induce collider bias and are rarely reported. People may choose where to live based on health,
485 socioeconomic status, or related factors, which can affect both exposure to animal feeding
486 operations and respiratory health. While these residential self-selection processes are
487 conceptually represented in the reference DAG through upstream social determinants, they
488 were rarely measured or discussed in the reviewed studies. As a result, residual confounding
489 due to residential self-selection cannot be ruled out and is acknowledged as a remaining source

490 of bias. Third, substantial heterogeneity in exposure definitions, outcome ascertainment, and
491 measurement timing across studies limits the ability to verify assumed causal pathways or
492 ensure comparability of adjustment sets. Finally, DAG-based assessments cannot overcome
493 incomplete reporting of study design or analytic decisions in primary studies and should
494 therefore be interpreted as identifying possible, rather than definitive, sources of bias. Together,
495 these limitations highlight that DAG-based evaluations enhance transparency but do not
496 eliminate fundamental uncertainties inherent in observational evidence synthesis. Beyond
497 confounding and collider bias, DAGs can also be used to conceptualize other sources of bias
498 relevant to evidence synthesis, including selection processes related to study participation, loss
499 to follow-up, or conditioning on study inclusion, provided these mechanisms can be plausibly
500 represented within the assumed causal structure.

501

502 **CONCLUSIONS**

503 Confounding remains a central challenge in observational studies examining the health effects
504 of residential proximity to AFOs. This study demonstrates that incorporating DAGs into bias
505 assessment can highlight ambiguities in the causal interpretation of commonly used control
506 strategies, particularly when causal assumptions are not explicitly stated. We do not conclude
507 that the existing literature is uniformly biased; rather, we conclude that its interpretation would
508 be strengthened by clearer articulation of hypothesized causal structures.

509 We encourage authors of future studies in this area to develop, discuss, and report their causal
510 diagrams or equivalent frameworks. Doing so would enhance transparency, facilitate more
511 informative evidence synthesis, and strengthen the contribution of this literature to public health
512 decision-making.

513

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518

519 **Disclosure statement**

520 See EBT declarations documents

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522

523 **FIGURES**

524

525 Figure 1. Directed acyclic graph (DAG) from Brewer et al. (2017) illustrating hypothesized causal and
526 biasing pathways linking exposure to animal feeding operation (AFO) emissions, with odor included in the
527 DAG as a proxy exposure, and lower respiratory disease (chronic bronchitis) as the outcome. Arrows
528 indicate assumed causal direction and temporal ordering between variables. The DAG includes contextual
529 determinants (e.g., socioeconomic status, land use/zoning), exposure, intermediate biological and
530 psychosocial processes, behavioral factors, and the health outcome. Causal pathways represent direct and
531 indirect mechanisms through which exposure may influence disease, while non-causal (backdoor)
532 pathways illustrate potential sources of confounding and collider bias. The DAG is used as a reference
533 framework to evaluate control strategies reported in primary studies, rather than as a synthesized or study-
534 specific causal model. © Brewer et al (2017), used with permission under license number 5563820571671.

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545 Figure 2. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Radon et al. (2005), mapped onto the population-
 546 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 547 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 548 evaluated using DAGitty.net.

549

550 Figure 3. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Mirabelli et al., 2006, mapped onto the population-
 551 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 552 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 553 evaluated using DAGitty.net. ** Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes
 554 reported where Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year, self-
 555 reported allergies, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in past year all
 556 children, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in the past year self-reported
 557 allergies. Other outcomes evaluated: Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization
 558 in past year, self-reported allergies, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in

559 past year all children, Asthma-related physician visit emergency visit and/or hospitalization in the past year
 560 self-reported allergies.
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562
 563 Figure 4. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Hoopmann et al 2006, mapped onto the
 564 population-level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure
 565 to animal feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was
 566 recreated and evaluated using DAGitty.net. ** Other outcomes assessed for this exposure are listed
 567 below, as well as the model code. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other lower
 568 respiratory outcomes reported were Allergic asthma-atopic parents, non-allergic asthma-non-atopic
 569 parents, non-allergic asthma-Atopic parents, Asthmatic Pathology-Not-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic
 570 Pathology-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology, IgE. Other outcomes evaluated: Allergic asthma-atopic
 571 parents, non-allergic asthma-non-atopic parents, non-allergic asthma-Atopic parents, Asthmatic
 572 Pathology-Not-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology-Atopic Parents, Asthmatic Pathology, IgE.

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574

575 Figure 5. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Radon et al 2007, mapped onto the population-
 576 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 577 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 578 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other
 579 outcomes reported were: Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness to Methacholine, Physician-Diagnosed Asthma.
 580 Other outcomes evaluated: Bronchial Hyperresponsiveness to Methacholine, Physician-Diagnosed
 581 Asthma.

582

583 Figure 6. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Hooiveld et al 2016, mapped onto the population-
 584 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 585 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 586 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other
 587 outcomes reported were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD)

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589

590 Figure 7. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Freidl et al 2017, mapped onto the population-level
 591 causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal feeding
 592 operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and evaluated
 593 using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide. Other outcomes reported
 594 were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Other exposures
 595 evaluated: Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 1000m of residence, Presence of
 596 farm with minimum amount of animals within 1500m of residence, Presence of farm with minimum
 597 amount of animals within 2000m of residence, Distance (quartiles expressed in meters) between
 598 residence and closest farm with minimum 250 poultry, Distance (quartiles expressed in meters) between
 599 residence and closest farm with minimum 50 goats, Number of animals within 1000m of the residence,
 600 Number of farms (any type) within 1000m of residence.

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602

603 Figure 8. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Rasmussen et al 2017, mapped onto the
 604 population-level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure
 605 to animal feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was

606 recreated and evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide;
 607 SES = socioeconomic status. Other outcomes reported were Physician-Diagnosed Asthma, Chronic
 608 obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Other outcomes evaluated: Asthma emergency department
 609 visits, new asthma oral corticosteroid orders.

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611

612 Figure 9. DAG illustrating the control strategy used by Schultz et al 2019, mapped onto the population-
 613 level causal structure proposed by Brewer et al. (2017) for the association between exposure to animal
 614 feeding operation (AFO)-related emissions and lower respiratory disease. The DAG was recreated and
 615 evaluated using DAGitty.net. **. Abbreviations: NH3 = ammonia; H2S = hydrogen sulfide; SES =
 616 socioeconomic status. Other outcomes reported were Nasal or lung allergies & current asthma, Current
 617 asthma, Asthma (at least 1 episode in past year), Asthma medication use in the past year, Physician-
 618 Diagnosed Asthma.

619

620 Table 1: Characteristics of 17 relevant studies (listed chronologically from most recent)
 621 providing comparative estimates of the incidence of health outcomes and residential proximity to
 622 AFOs.

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Simões et al. 2022)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home	Lower respiratory
(Fisher et al. 2020)	USA	Number of livestock near the home	Cancer
(van Kersen et al. 2020)	Netherlands	Levels of PM ₁₀ and NH ₃	Lower respiratory
(Schultz et al. 2019)	USA	Proximity of home to nearest AFO	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory
(Poulsen et al. 2018)	USA	Poultry operation activity	Gastrointestinal condition
(Freidl et al. 2017)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home Distance of home from nearest AFO	Lower respiratory
(Rasmussen et al. 2017)	USA	Proximity of home to nearest AFO	Lower respiratory
(Hooiveld et al. 2016)	Netherlands	Number of AFOs near the home	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory Infectious condition Skin condition

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Nava Cortes et al. 2015)	Mexico	Proximity of home to an AFO	Infectious condition
(Levallois et al. 2014)	Canada	Density of livestock near the home	Gastrointestinal condition
(Schinasi et al. 2014)	USA	Number of livestock near the home Proximity of home to an AFO Detected AFO odors while at home	Antimicrobial resistance
(Smit et al. 2012)	Netherlands	Number of livestock near the home Proximity of home to an AFO	Lower respiratory Infectious conditions
(Horton et al. 2009)	USA	Pollution levels Odor rating	Psychiatric disorder
(Radon et al. 2007)	Germany	Odor rating Number of AFOs near the home	Lower respiratory
(Hoopmann et al. 2006)	Germany	Pollution levels	Lower respiratory
(Mirabelli et al. 2006)	USA	Density of livestock near school Odor rating Distance from nearest AFO	Lower respiratory

Study	Country	Exposure categories	Outcome categories
(Radon et al. 2005)	Germany	Proximity of home to nearest AFO Odor rating	Lower respiratory Upper respiratory

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625

626 Table 2. Summary of variables controlled for in relevant studies that provide estimates of the
 627 incidence of lower respiratory tract conditions.

Study	Variables controlled
(Schultz et al. 2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Poverty to income ratio (mapped to SES) • Education (mapped) • BMI (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Smoking status (mapped to smoking) • Pet ownership (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Proximity to major roadways (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Freidl et al. 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Rasmussen et al. 2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race/ethnicity (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Family history of asthma (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Smoking status (mapped to Smoking) • Medical Assistance (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Overweight/obesity (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Type 2 diabetes (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community socioeconomic deprivation (mapped to SES) • Distance to nearest major and minor arterial road (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Squared distance to nearest major and minor arterial road (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Distance to nearest Geisinger hospital (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Squared distance to nearest Geisinger hospital (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Age category (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Sex (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Year of event (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Hooiveld et al. 2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Age, polynomial (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Registry duration (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Number of inhabitants in the postal code area and total surface area (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Radon et al. 2007)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Active and Passive smoke exposure (mapped to smoking) • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Level of education (mapped to education level) • Number of siblings (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parental allergies (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Sex (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Hoopmann et al. 2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Oldest sibling (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Experienced Street noise (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Actual smoking (mapped to smoking) • Education level (mapped onto education level) • Breastfed at least 4 months (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Mold (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Contact with cats at a young age not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Rug/carpeted floor (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)
(Mirabelli et al. 2006)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Race (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Use of gas stove (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Allergy status not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Hispanic ethnicity (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG)

Study	Variables controlled
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic status (mapped to SES) • Smoking status (mapped to smoking) • Exposure to secondhand smoke at home (mapped to smoking)
(Radon et al. 2005)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Allergies of parents (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Gender (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Higher education status (mapped to education level) • Second-hand smoke exposure (mapped to smoking) • Number of siblings (not represented in the Brewer et al. (2017) reference DAG) • Smoker-status (mapped to smoking)

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630 **REFERENCES**

631

632 Bours, M.J.L., 2021. Tutorial: A nontechnical explanation of the counterfactual definition of effect
633 modification and interaction. *J Clin Epidemiol* 134, 113–124.

634 Churilov, L., Hayward, K., Yogendrakumar, V., Andrew, N., 2025. Conducting descriptive
635 epidemiology and causal inference studies using observational data: A 10-point primer for
636 stroke researchers. *Eur Stroke J* 23969873251332120.

637 Correia, L.C.L., Mascarenhas, R.F., De Menezes, F.S.C., Oliveira, J.S., Vaccarino, V., Ross,
638 J.S., Wallach, J.D., 2025. Confounder selection in observational studies in high-impact
639 medical and epidemiological journals. *JAMA Netw Open* 8, e2524176–e2524176.

640 Digitale, J.C., Martin, J.N., Glidden, D. V, Glymour, M.M., 2023. Key concepts in clinical
641 epidemiology: collider-conditioning bias. *J Clin Epidemiol* 161, 152–156.

642 Digitale, J.C., Martin, J.N., Glymour, M.M., 2022. Tutorial on directed acyclic graphs. *J Clin*
643 *Epidemiol* 142, 264–267.

644 Dijk, S.W., Caulley, L.M., Hunink, M., Labrecque, J., 2024. From complexity to clarity: how
645 directed acyclic graphs enhance the study design of systematic reviews and meta-
646 analyses. *Eur J Epidemiol* 39, 27–33.

647 Ferguson, K.D., McCann, M., Katikireddi, S.V., Thomson, H., Green, M.J., Smith, D.J., Lewsey,
648 J.D., 2020. Evidence synthesis for constructing directed acyclic graphs (ESC-DAGs): a
649 novel and systematic method for building directed acyclic graphs. *Int J Epidemiol* 49, 322–
650 329.

651 Gail, M.H., Altman, D.G., Cadarette, S.M., Collins, G., Evans, S.J.W., Sekula, P., Williamson,
652 E., Woodward, M., 2019. Design choices for observational studies of the effect of exposure
653 on disease incidence. *BMJ Open* 9, e031031.

654 Hernán, M.A., Robins, J.M., 2020. *Causal Inference: What If*.

655 Knol, M.J., Vandenbroucke, J.P., Scott, P., Egger, M., 2008. What do case-control studies
656 estimate? Survey of methods and assumptions in published case-control research. *Am J*
657 *Epidemiol* 168, 1073–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwn217>

658 Parra, C.O., Bertizzolo, L., Schroter, S., Dechartres, A., Goetghebeur, E., 2021. Consistency of
659 causal claims in observational studies: a review of papers published in a general medical
660 journal. *BMJ Open* 11, e043339.

661 Pearce, N., 2004. Effect measures in prevalence studies. *Environ Health Perspect* 112, 1047–
662 50. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.6927>

663 Reichenheim, M.E., Coutinho, E.S.F., 2010. Measures and models for causal inference in
664 cross-sectional studies: arguments for the appropriateness of the prevalence odds ratio
665 and related logistic regression. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 10, 66.
666 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-66>

667 Sauer, B., VanderWeele, T.J., 2013. Use of directed acyclic graphs, in: *Developing a Protocol
668 for Observational Comparative Effectiveness Research: A User's Guide*. Agency for
669 Healthcare Research and Quality (US).

670 Shrier, I., Platt, R.W., 2008. Reducing bias through directed acyclic graphs. *BMC Med Res
671 Methodol* 8, 70.

672 Tennant, P.W.G., Murray, E.J., Arnold, K.F., Berrie, L., Fox, M.P., Gadd, S.C., Harrison, W.J.,
673 Keeble, C., Ranker, L.R., Textor, J., 2021. Use of directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to
674 identify confounders in applied health research: review and recommendations. *Int J
675 Epidemiol* 50, 620–632.

676 Williams, T.C., Bach, C.C., Matthiesen, N.B., Henriksen, T.B., Gagliardi, L., 2018. Directed
677 acyclic graphs: a tool for causal studies in paediatrics. *Pediatr Res* 84, 487–493.

678 Arksey, H.; O'Malley, L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International
679 Journal of Social Research Methodology* 2005;8:19-32

680 Borlee, F.; Yzermans, C.J.; van Dijk, C.E.; Heederik, D.; Smit, L.A. Increased respiratory
681 symptoms in COPD patients living in the vicinity of livestock farms. *Eur Respir J*
682 2015;46:1605-1614

683 Brewer, L.E.; Wright, J.M.; Rice, G.; Neas, L.; Teuschler, L. Causal inference in cumulative risk
684 assessment: The roles of directed acyclic graphs. *Environ Int* 2017;102:30-41

685 Cole, D.; Todd, L.; Wing, S. Concentrated swine feeding operations and public health: a review
686 of occupational and community health effects. *Environ Health Perspect* 2000;108:685-
687 699

688 Cole, S.R.; Platt, R.W.; Schisterman, E.F.; Chu, H.; Westreich, D.; Richardson, D.; Poole, C.
689 Illustrating bias due to conditioning on a collider. *Int J Epidemiol* 2010;39:417-420
690 Didelez, V.; Stensrud, M.J. On the logic of collapsibility for causal effect measures. *Biom J*
691 2022;64:235-242
692 Dijk, S.W., Caulley, L.M., Hunink, M., Labrecque, J., 2024. From complexity to clarity: how
693 directed acyclic graphs enhance the study design of systematic reviews and meta-
694 analyses. *Eur J Epidemiol* 39, 27–33
695 Douglas, P.; Robertson, S.; Gay, R.; Hansell, A.L.; Gant, T.W. A systematic review of the public
696 health risks of bioaerosols from intensive farming. *Int J Hyg Environ Health*
697 2018;221:134-173
698 Ferguson, K.D.; McCann, M.; Katikireddi, S.V.; Thomson, H.; Green, M.J.; Smith, D.J.; Lewsey,
699 J.D. Evidence synthesis for constructing directed acyclic graphs (ESC-DAGs): a novel
700 and systematic method for building directed acyclic graphs. *Int J Epidemiol* 2020;49:322-
701 329
702 Fisher, J.A.; Freeman, L.E.B.; Hofmann, J.N.; Blair, A.; Parks, C.G.; Thorne, P.S.; Ward, M.H.;
703 Jones, R.R. Residential Proximity to Intensive Animal Agriculture and Risk of
704 Lymphohematopoietic Cancers in the Agricultural Health Study. *Epidemiology*
705 (Cambridge, Mass) 2020;31:478-489
706 Freidl, G.S.; Spruijt, I.T.; Borlee, F.; Smit, L.A.M.; Gageldonk-Lafeber, A.B.v.; Heederik, D.J.J.;
707 Yzermans, J.; Dijk, C.E.v.; Maassen, C.B.M.; Hoek, W.v.d. Livestock-associated risk
708 factors for pneumonia in an area of intensive animal farming in the Netherlands. *PLoS*
709 *ONE* 2017;12:e0174796
710 Guo, Y.; Ryan, U.; Feng, Y.; Xiao, L. Association of Common Zoonotic Pathogens With
711 Concentrated Animal Feeding Operations. *Front Microbiol* 2021;12:810142
712 Higgins, J.P.T.; Morgan, R.L.; Rooney, A.A.; Taylor, K.W.; Thayer, K.A.; Silva, R.A.; Lemeris,
713 C.; Akl, E.A.; Bateson, T.F.; Berkman, N.D.; Glenn, B.S.; Hrobjartsson, A.; LaKind, J.S.;
714 McAleenan, A.; Meerpohl, J.J.; Nachman, R.M.; Obbagy, J.E.; O'Connor, A.; Radke,
715 E.G.; Savovic, J.; Schunemann, H.J.; Shea, B.; Tilling, K.; Verbeek, J.; Viswanathan, M.;
716 Sterne, J.A.C. A tool to assess risk of bias in non-randomized follow-up studies of
717 exposure effects (ROBINS-E). *Environ Int* 2024;186:108602
718 Hooiveld, M.; Smit, L.A.M.; Sman-de Beer, F.v.d.; Wouters, I.M.; Dijk, C.E.v.; Spreeuwenberg,
719 P.; Heederik, D.J.J.; Yzermans, C.J. Doctor-diagnosed health problems in a region with
720 a high density of concentrated animal feeding operations: a cross-sectional study.
721 *Environmental Health* 2016;15:(17 February 2016)

722 Hoopmann, M.; Hehl, O.; Neisel, F.; Werfel, T. Associations between bioaerosols coming from
723 livestock facilities and asthmatic symptoms in children. *Gesundheitswesen*
724 (Bundesverband der Ärzte des Öffentlichen Gesundheitsdienstes (Germany))
725 2006;68:575-584

726 Horton, R.A.; Wing, S.; Marshall, S.W.; Brownley, K.A. Malodor as a trigger of stress and
727 negative mood in neighbors of industrial hog operations. *American journal of public*
728 *health* 2009;99:S610-S615

729 Huitfeldt, A.; Stensrud, M.J.; Suzuki, E. On the collapsibility of measures of effect in the
730 counterfactual causal framework. *Emerg Themes Epidemiol* 2019;16:1

731 Knol, M.J., Vandenbroucke, J.P., Scott, P., Egger, M., 2008. What do case-control studies
732 estimate? Survey of methods and assumptions in published case-control research. *Am J*
733 *Epidemiol* 168, 1073–81. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwn217>

734 Levac, D.; Colquhoun, H.; O'Brien, K.K. Scoping studies: advancing the methodology.
735 *Implement Sci* 2010;5:69

736 Levallois, P.; Chevalier, P.; Gingras, S.; Dery, P.; Payment, P.; Michel, P.; Rodriguez, M. Risk of
737 infectious gastroenteritis in young children living in quebec rural areas with intensive
738 animal farming: results of a case-control study (2004-2007). *Zoonoses and Public Health*
739 2014;61:28-38

740 Martinez, B.A.F. Animal Feeding Operations and Health Effects on People Living in the
741 Surrounding Areas: A Comprehensive Analysis. . Department of Large Animal Clinician
742 Sciences: Michigan State University 2023

743 McElroy, K.G. Environmental health effects of concentrated animal feeding operations:
744 implications for nurses. *Nurs Adm Q* 2010;34:311-319

745 Mirabelli, M.C.; Wing, S.; Marshall, S.W.; Wilcosky, T.C. Asthma symptoms among adolescents
746 who attend public schools that are located near confined swine feeding operations.
747 *Pediatrics* 2006;118:e66-e75

748 Moore, T.C.; Fong, J.; Rosa Hernandez, A.M.; Pogreba-Brown, K. CAFOs, novel influenza, and
749 the need for One Health approaches. *One Health* 2021;13:100246

750 Nava Cortes, N.; Romero Nunez, C.; Bautista Gomez, L.G.; Hernandez Garcia, P.A.; Heredia
751 Cardenas, R. Presence of anti-Toxocara canis antibodies and risk factors in children
752 from the Amecameca and Chalco regions of Mexico. *BMC Pediatrics* 2015;15:(30 May
753 2015)

754 Noah, N. The STROBE initiative: STrengthening the Reporting of OBservational studies in
755 *Epidemiology (STROBE)*. *Epidemiol Infect* 2008;136:865

756 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.; Bickett-Weddle, D.; Kirkhorn, S.; Sargeant, J.M.; Ramirez, A.;
757 Von Essen, S.G. The association between proximity to animal feeding operations and
758 community health: a systematic review. *PLoS One* 2010;5:e9530

759 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.W.; Dzikamunhenga, R.S.; Glanville, J.M.; Higgins, J.P.T.;
760 Kirychuk, S.P.; Sargeant, J.M.; Totton, S.C.; Wood, H.; Von Essen, S.G. Updated
761 systematic review: associations between proximity to animal feeding operations and
762 health of individuals in nearby communities. *Syst Rev* 2017;6:86

763 O'Connor, A.M.; Auvermann, B.W.; Higgins, J.P.; Kirychuk, S.P.; Sargeant, J.M.; Von Essen,
764 S.G.; Glanville, J.M.; Wood, H. The association between proximity to animal-feeding
765 operations and community health: a protocol for updating a systematic review. *Syst Rev*
766 2014;3:99

767 Pearce, N., 2004. Effect measures in prevalence studies. *Environ Health Perspect* 112, 1047–
768 50. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.6927>

769 Polzer, I.; Schwahn, C.; Volzke, H.; Mundt, T.; Biffar, R. The association of tooth loss with all-
770 cause and circulatory mortality. Is there a benefit of replaced teeth? A systematic review
771 and meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Investig* 2012;16:333-351

772 Poulsen, M.N.; Pollak, J.; Sills, D.L.; Casey, J.A.; Rasmussen, S.G.; Nachman, K.E.; Cosgrove,
773 S.E.; Stewart, D.; Schwartz, B.S. Residential proximity to high-density poultry operations
774 associated with campylobacteriosis and infectious diarrhea. *International Journal of*
775 *Hygiene and Environmental Health* 2018;221:323-333

776 Radon, K.; Schulze, A.; Ehrenstein, V.; van Strien, R.T.; Praml, G.; Nowak, D. Environmental
777 exposure to confined animal feeding operations and respiratory health of neighboring
778 residents. *Epidemiology* 2007:300-308

779 Radon, K.; Schulze, A.; Strien, R.; Ehrenstein, V.; Praml, G.; Nowak, D. [Prevalence of
780 respiratory symptoms and diseases in neighbours of large-scale farming in Northern
781 Germany]. *Pneumologie* 2005;59:897-900

782 Rasmussen, S.G.; Casey, J.A.; Bandeen-Roche, K.; Schwartz, B.S. Proximity to Industrial Food
783 Animal Production and Asthma Exacerbations in Pennsylvania, 2005-2012. *International*
784 *journal of environmental research and public health* 2017;14

785 Reichenheim, M.E., Coutinho, E.S.F., 2010. Measures and models for causal inference in
786 cross-sectional studies: arguments for the appropriateness of the prevalence odds ratio
787 and related logistic regression. *BMC Med Res Methodol* 10, 66.
788 <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-10-66>

789 Savitz, D.A.; Wellenius, G.A. Can Cross-Sectional Studies Contribute to Causal Inference? It
790 Depends. *Am J Epidemiol* 2023;192:514-516

791 Schinasi, L.; Wing, S.; Augustino, K.L.; Ramsey, K.M.; Nobles, D.L.; Richardson, D.B.; Price,
792 L.B.; Aziz, M.; MacDonald, P.D.M.; Stewart, J.R. A case control study of environmental
793 and occupational exposures associated with methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*
794 nasal carriage in patients admitted to a rural tertiary care hospital in a high density swine
795 region. *Environmental Health* 2014;13:1-12

796 Schultz, A.A.; Peppard, P.; Gangnon, R.E.; Malecki, K.M.C. Residential proximity to
797 concentrated animal feeding operations and allergic and respiratory disease.
798 *Environment International* 2019;130:104911

799 Simões, M.; Janssen, N.; Heederik, D.J.J.; Smit, L.A.M.; Vermeulen, R.; Huss, A. Residential
800 proximity to livestock animals and mortality from respiratory diseases in The
801 Netherlands: A prospective census-based cohort study. *Environment international*
802 2022;161:107140

803 Smit, L.A.; Hooiveld, M.; van der Sman-de Beer, F.; Opstal-van Winden, A.W.; Beekhuizen, J.;
804 Wouters, I.M.; Yzermans, C.J.; Heederik, D. Air pollution from livestock farms, and
805 asthma, allergic rhinitis and COPD among neighbouring residents. *Occup Environ Med*
806 2014;71:134-140

807 Smit, L.A.M.; van der Sman-de Beer, F.; Opstal-van Winden, A.W.J.; Hooiveld, M.; Beekhuizen,
808 J.; Wouters, I.M.; Yzermans, J.; Heederik, D. Q fever and pneumonia in an area with a
809 high livestock density: a large population-based study. *PloS one* 2012;7:e38843

810 Sweeten, J.; Miner, R.; Tengman, C. Fact Sheet #1: A Brief History and Background of the EPA
811 CAFO Rule in: curriculum R.f.L.a.P.E.S., ed; 2003

812 Tennant, P.W.G.; Murray, E.J.; Arnold, K.F.; Berrie, L.; Fox, M.P.; Gadd, S.C.; Harrison, W.J.;
813 Keeble, C.; Ranker, L.R.; Textor, J.; Tomova, G.D.; Gilthorpe, M.S.; Ellison, G.T.H. Use
814 of directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) to identify confounders in applied health research:
815 review and recommendations. *Int J Epidemiol* 2021;50:620-632

816 Textor, J.; Hardt, J.; Knuppel, S. DAGitty: a graphical tool for analyzing causal diagrams.
817 *Epidemiology* 2011;22:745

818 Textor, J.; van der Zander, B.; Gilthorpe, M.S.; Liskiewicz, M.; Ellison, G.T. Robust causal
819 inference using directed acyclic graphs: the R package 'dagitty'. *Int J Epidemiol*
820 2016;45:1887-1894

821 Tiwari S, Chhapola V, Chaudhary N, Sharma L. Directed acyclic graph helps to understand the
822 causality of malnutrition in under-5 children born small for gestational age. *J Clin*

823 Epidemiol. 2025 Jan;177:111611. doi: 10.1016/j.jclinepi.2024.111611. Epub 2024 Nov
824 16. PMID: 39551398

825 Thu, K.M. Public health concerns for neighbors of large-scale swine production operations. J
826 Agric Saf Health 2002;8:175-184

827 van Kersen, W.; Oldenwening, M.; Aalders, B.; Bloemsma, L.D.; Borlee, F.; Heederik, D.; Smit,
828 L.A.M. Acute respiratory effects of livestock-related air pollution in a panel of COPD
829 patients. Environment international 2020;136:105426

830 von Elm, E.; Altman, D.G.; Egger, M.; Pocock, S.J.; Gotsche, P.C.; Vandenbroucke, J.P.;
831 Initiative, S. The Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology
832 (STROBE) statement: guidelines for reporting observational studies. J Clin Epidemiol
833 2008;61:344-349

834

835

836 **SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIAL**

837

838 This section reiterates key causal concepts introduced in the main text for pedagogical
839 completeness.

840

841 **Illustration of DAG concepts using the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG**

842 To illustrate how directed acyclic graphs (DAGs) were used in this study, we use the DAG
843 published by Brewer et al. (2017), which hypothesizes causal relationships between exposure to
844 emissions from animal feeding operations (AFOs), with odor included in the DAG as a proxy
845 exposure, and chronic bronchitis (Figure 1). This DAG was used as an illustrative example to
846 demonstrate key causal concepts relevant to bias assessment in observational studies.

847 The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG includes different types of variables (nodes) and directed edges
848 that represent hypothesized causal relationships between upstream contextual factors,
849 exposure, intermediate processes, and the health outcome. In DAGs, arrows encode temporal
850 and causal ordering, such that a parent node is assumed to precede its child node in time and
851 cannot be caused by it. Although DAGitty does not assign explicit time stamps, temporality is
852 enforced by the direction of arrows and the requirement that the graph remains acyclic.

853 **Causal pathways and temporality**

854 Within the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, causal pathways represent direct or indirect mechanisms
855 through which exposure may influence the outcome, while biasing (non-causal) pathways
856 connect exposure and outcome through alternative routes that may introduce confounding or
857 collider bias.

858 The DAG includes a direct causal pathway, represented as:

- 859
- Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Chronic Bronchitis

860 This pathway encodes the assumption that exposure precedes disease onset and does not
861 involve intermediate variables.

862 The DAG also specifies several indirect causal pathways, which represent temporally ordered
863 sequences of events through intermediate variables, for example:

- 864
- Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Bronchial irritation → Lung inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Oxide →
865 Chronic Bronchitis

- 866 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
867 → Chronic Bronchitis
868 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
869 → Lung inflammation → Exhaled Nitric Oxide → Chronic Bronchitis

870 Together, the direct and indirect causal pathways constitute the total causal effect of exposure
871 on the outcome. Temporality is encoded through the directionality of the arrows, ensuring that
872 exposure precedes perception, stress, behavior, biological changes, and ultimately disease.

873 **Biasing pathways and confounding**

874 The DAG also includes biasing (backdoor) pathways, which are non-causal routes linking
875 exposure and outcome through common causes. For example:

- 876 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) ← AFO ← Land Use/Zoning ← Socioeconomic Status (SES) →
877 Education Level → Smoking → Chronic Bronchitis

878 In this pathway, SES is a potential confounder because it influences both proximity to AFOs (via
879 land use and zoning decisions) and downstream determinants of respiratory health, such as
880 education and smoking. In DAG terminology, this represents a *backdoor path* connecting the
881 exposure and outcome. To estimate the causal effect of exposure on outcome, such paths must
882 be blocked, typically by controlling for appropriate confounding variables.

883 **Colliders and collider bias**

884 The Brewer et al. (2017) DAG also illustrates collider structures. For example:

- 885 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking ← Education Level
886 ← SES

887 In this structure, Smoking is a collider because it has two incoming arrows from independent
888 causal pathways: one originating from exposure-related stress and the other from
889 socioeconomic determinants via education. Conditioning on a collider (e.g., adjusting for
890 smoking in a regression model) can open an otherwise closed path between exposure and
891 outcome, inducing a spurious association—this is known as collider bias (Cole et al., 2010;
892 Digitale et al., 2023).

893 Importantly, collider status cannot be inferred solely from the presence of two incoming arrows;
894 it depends on whether those arrows represent independent pathways connecting exposure and
895 outcome. In contrast, variables such as Lung Inflammation or Chronic Individual Stress,
896 although they receive multiple arrows, do not act as colliders in this specific exposure–outcome

897 relationship because they lie along a single causal sequence rather than at the intersection of
898 independent paths.

899 **Mediators and target causal effects**

900 Some variables in the DAG function as mediators, meaning they lie on the causal pathway
901 between exposure and outcome. For example:

- 902 • Odors (NH₃, H₂S) → Perception of Health Risk → Chronic Individual Stress → Smoking
903 → Chronic Bronchitis

904 Perception of health risk and chronic individual stress are mediators in this pathway.

905 Conditioning on mediators blocks part of the causal effect and therefore prevents estimation of
906 the total effect, yielding instead an estimate closer to the direct effect. Adjusting for mediators is
907 not inherently incorrect, but it must be aligned with the study's causal estimand and explicitly
908 justified (Tennant et al., 2021).

909 **Minimum sufficient set of control variables**

910 A minimum sufficient set of control variables is the smallest set of variables that, when
911 controlled for, blocks all non-causal (backdoor) paths between exposure and outcome without
912 blocking causal pathways or opening collider paths. Identification of such sets involves
913 examining all paths connecting exposure and outcome in the DAG and selecting variables that
914 close confounding paths while preserving causal ones.

915 In the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG, multiple minimum sufficient sets of control variables exist for
916 estimating the total causal effect of AFO exposure on chronic bronchitis. Specifically, either of
917 the following single-variable sets is sufficient:

- 918 • Minimum sufficient set of control variables 1: Education Level
- 919 • Minimum sufficient set of control variables 2: Land Use/Zoning

920 The existence of multiple valid sets of control variables reflects the structure of the hypothesized
921 causal relationships and offers alternative strategies depending on data availability and
922 feasibility. If AFO presence itself is unobserved, as assumed in the original Brewer et al. (2017)
923 DAG, adjusting for either education level or land use/zoning is sufficient to block the relevant
924 backdoor paths and obtain an unbiased estimate of the total effect under the assumed causal
925 structure.

926

927 **Brewer et al 2017 DAGitty code**
928
929 dag {
930 bb="0,0,1,1"
931 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.581,0.340"]
932 "Chronic Bronchitis" [outcome,pos="0.965,0.369"]
933 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
934 "Education Level" [pos="0.171,0.564"]
935 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.851,0.400"]
936 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.595,0.436"]
937 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
938 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.729,0.413"]
939 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
940 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
941 "Socioeconomic Status" [latent,pos="0.050,0.500"]
942 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
943 Smoking [pos="0.669,0.648"]
944 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
945 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
946 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking
947 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
948 "Education Level" -> Smoking
949 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis"
950 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"

951 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
952 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
953 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"
954 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis"
955 "Odors (NH3, H2S)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"
956 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
957 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
958 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
959 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S)"
960 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis"
961 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"
962 }

963 **DAGitty code for mapping Radon et al. (2005) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG**

964
965 dag {
966 bb="0,0,1,1"
967 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
968 "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
969 [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
970 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
971 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]
972 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
973 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]
974 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
975 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
976 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)"
977 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
978 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

979 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
980 "Socioeconomic Status" [latent,pos="0.062,0.496"]
981 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
982 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
983 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
984 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)"
985 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" -> "Chronic Stress"
986 "Education Level (Higher Education Status)" -> "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status,
987 Smoker Status)"
988 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
989 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
990 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
991 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
992 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Bronchial
993 Irritation"
994 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Chronic
995 Bronchitis (Non-Cold Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
996 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)" -> "Perceived
997 Health Risk"
998 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
999 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Non-Cold
1000 Related Rhonchal Breathing Sounds) "
1001 "Smoking (Second-hand Exposure Status, Smoker Status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1002 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level (Higher Education Status)"
1003 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1004 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Animal Houses within 500 m, Level of Odor Annoyance)"
1005 }

1006 **DAGitty code for mapping Mirabelli et al. (2006) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
1007 **DAG**

1008

1009 dag {

1010 bb="0,0,1,1"

1011 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1012 "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"
1013 [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1014 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1015 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]

1016 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1017 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1018 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1019 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1020 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1021 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1022 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) "
1023 [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]

1024 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" [adjusted,pos="0.099,0.479"]

1025 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]

1026 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1027 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"

1028 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) "

1029 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"

1030 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) "

1031 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"

1032 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1033 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO

1034 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"

1035 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"

1036 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Missed School Last Year as
1037 Result of Asthma)"

1038 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"

1039 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"

1040 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) " -> "Chronic Bronchitis
1041 (Missed School Last Year as Result of Asthma)"

1042 "Smoking (Smoking Status, Exposure to Second-hand Smoke at Home) " -> "Lung
1043 Inflammation"

1044 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" -> "Education Level"

1045 "Socioeconomic Status (Economic Status)" -> "Land use/Zoning"

1046 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Livestock Odor)"

1047 }

1048 **DAGitty code for mapping Hoopmann et al. (2006) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
1049 **DAG**

1050

1051 dag {

1052 bb="0,0,1,1"

1053 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1054 "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) " [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1055 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1056 "Education Level" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]

1057 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1058 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1059 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1060 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1061 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1062 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1063 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]

1064 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]

1065 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]

1066 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1067 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
 1068 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Actual Smoking) "
 1069 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
 1070 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Actual Smoking) "
 1071 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
 1072 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1073 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
 1074 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
 1075 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"
 1076 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
 1077 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"
 1078 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
 1079 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Allergic Asthma) "
 1080 "Smoking (Actual Smoking) " -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1081 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
 1082 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
 1083 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Log of Endotoxin)"
 1084 }
 1085
 1086 **DAGitty code for mapping Hooiveld et al. (2016) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
 1087 **DAG**
 1088
 1089 dag {
 1090 bb="0,0,1,1"
 1091 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
 1092 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
 1093 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
 1094 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]
 1095 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
 1096 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1097 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1098 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1099 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)"
1100 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1101 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1102 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]
1103 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1104 Smoking [pos="0.566,0.611"]
1105 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1106 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1107 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking
1108 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1109 "Education Level" -> Smoking
1110 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1111 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1112 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1113 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1114 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1115 "Bronchial Irritation"
1116 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1117 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1118 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the residence)" ->
1119 "Perceived Health Risk"
1120 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1121 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
1122 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1123 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Each additional CAFO within the postal code area of the
1124 residence)"
1125 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia **)"
1126 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"
1127 }
1128

1129 **DAGitty code for mapping Freidl et al. (2017) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017) DAG**

1130

1131 dag {

1132 bb="0,0,1,1"

1133 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]

1134 "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]

1135 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]

1136 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]

1137 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]

1138 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1139 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]

1140 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]

1141 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of
1142 residence **)" [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]

1143 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]

1144 "Socioeconomic Status" [pos="0.073,0.483"]

1145 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]

1146 Smoking [pos="0.566,0.611"]

1147 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1148 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"

1149 "Chronic Stress" -> Smoking

1150 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"

1151 "Education Level" -> Smoking

1152 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" "

1153 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"

1154 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO

1155 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"

1156 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of
1157 residence **)" -> "Bronchial Irritation"

1158 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of
1159 residence **)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia)" "

1160 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m of
 1161 residence **)" -> "Perceived Health Risk"
 1162 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
 1163 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Education Level"
 1164 "Socioeconomic Status" -> "Land use/Zoning"
 1165 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Presence of farm with minimum amount of animals within 500 m
 1166 of residence **)"
 1167 Smoking -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Pneumonia) "
 1168 Smoking -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1169 }
 1170 **DAGitty code for mapping Rasmussen et al. (2017) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
 1171 **DAG**
 1172
 1173 dag {
 1174 bb="0,0,1,1"
 1175 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
 1176 "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
 1177 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
 1178 "Education Level" [pos="0.195,0.548"]
 1179 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
 1180 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]
 1181 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
 1182 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
 1183 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO) "
 1184 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
 1185 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
 1186 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" [adjusted,pos="0.109,0.461"]
 1187 "Smoking (Smoking status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
 1188 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
 1189 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1190 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"

1191 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
 1192 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
 1193 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
 1194 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
 1195 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1196 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
 1197 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
 1198 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
 1199 "Bronchial Irritation"
 1200 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
 1201 "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
 1202 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)" ->
 1203 "Perceived Health Risk"
 1204 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
 1205 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" -> "Education Level"
 1206 "SES (Community socioeconomic deprivation)" -> "Land use/Zoning"
 1207 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Asthma hospitalizations **)"
 1208 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
 1209 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Proximity of residential address to nearest swine or cattle CAFO)"
 1210 "
 1211 }
 1212 **DAGitty code for mapping Schultz et al. (2019) variables onto the Brewer et al. (2017)**
 1213 **DAG**
 1214
 1215 dag {
 1216 bb="0,0,1,1"
 1217 "Bronchial Irritation" [latent,pos="0.544,0.334"]
 1218 "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)" [outcome,pos="0.823,0.310"]
 1219 "Chronic Stress" [latent,pos="0.456,0.451"]
 1220 "Education Level" [adjusted,pos="0.195,0.548"]
 1221 "Exhaled NO" [pos="0.723,0.377"]
 1222 "Infection Susceptibility" [latent,pos="0.562,0.439"]

1223 "Land use/Zoning" [pos="0.149,0.378"]
1224 "Lung Inflammation" [latent,pos="0.662,0.408"]
1225 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)"
1226 [exposure,pos="0.299,0.201"]
1227 "Perceived Health Risk" [pos="0.375,0.344"]
1228 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" [adjusted,pos="0.085,0.461"]
1229 "Smoking (Smoking status)" [adjusted,pos="0.566,0.611"]
1230 CAFO [latent,pos="0.227,0.291"]
1231 "Bronchial Irritation" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1232 "Chronic Stress" -> "Infection Susceptibility"
1233 "Chronic Stress" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1234 "Education Level" -> "Chronic Stress"
1235 "Education Level" -> "Smoking (Smoking status)"
1236 "Exhaled NO" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1237 "Infection Susceptibility" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1238 "Land use/Zoning" -> CAFO
1239 "Lung Inflammation" -> "Exhaled NO"
1240 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1241 "Bronchial Irritation"
1242 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1243 "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1244 "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest CAFO)" ->
1245 "Perceived Health Risk"
1246 "Perceived Health Risk" -> "Chronic Stress"
1247 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" -> "Education Level"
1248 "SES (Poverty to income ratio)" -> "Land use/Zoning"
1249 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Chronic Bronchitis (Lung allergies **)"
1250 "Smoking (Smoking status)" -> "Lung Inflammation"
1251 CAFO -> "Odors (NH3, H2S) (Restricted cubic spline of residential distance to the nearest
1252 CAFO)"
1253 }

1254 Supplementary Table 1. Characteristics of relevant studies (listed chronologically from most
1255 recent) that provide estimates of the lower respiratory tract conditions.

Study	Country	Study Design
(Schultz et al. 2019)	USA	Cross-sectional
(Freidl et al. 2017)	Netherlands	Cross-sectional
(Rasmussen et al. 2017)	USA	Case-Control
(Hooiveld et al. 2016)	Netherlands	Cohort
(Radon et al. 2007)	Germany	Cross-sectional
(Hoopmann et al. 2006)	Germany	Cross-sectional
(Mirabelli et al. 2006)	USA	Cross-sectional
(Radon et al. 2005)	Germany	Cross-sectional

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1264 Supplementary Figure 1. Literature flow diagram for the living systematic review on the effects of
1265 animal feeding operations (AFOs) on the health of people living nearby. The diagram illustrates
1266 the number of records identified, screened, assessed for eligibility, excluded and included in the
1267 review.

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